

RNTWG: Packet Marking

This document focuses on the packet marking/labelling sub-task of the [Networking Technical Working group](#). It captures ongoing activities, ideas, technologies and brainstorming around packet marking (most of the content should be considered as a draft).

Mandate:

Analyzing the HEP traffic flows in detail is critical for understanding how the various complex systems developed by the LHC experiments are actually using the network. The potential work here is to identify how we might label our traffic to indicate which experiment and task it is a part of. This is especially important for sites which support many experiments simultaneously where any worker node or storage system may quickly change between different users. With a standardized way of marking traffic, any NREN or end-site could quickly provide detailed visibility into HEP traffic to and from their site.

There are two components for the technical work. One would encompass how to mark traffic at the network level, defining a standard set of markings and providing the tools to the experiments to make it easy for them to participate. We note that the increasing use of VMs and containers might make marking traffic easier where those technologies are in use. The second part of the work would involve identifying the required hardware and/or software and then conducting prototyping how to view the markings at line rate at any point on the path, and to act appropriately on (consume/store) the observed markings. Whatever method is proposed will also need associated tools and tests to validate that the marking is passed unaltered end to end. We will need the ability to make available various views, summaries and dashboards showing the details of the marked traffic, provided by the NRENs, end-sites or others involved with the packet flows. We will also need to fully document the validated architecture and its components. While the initial work is targeted at WLCG experiments, it is desirable that the approach can be used by other global R&E disciplines and their applications.

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Requirements and assumptions (to be discussed):

We assume the ability to mark/tag packets at the source, i.e. at the application or host level. This means the application will require information needed to determine what tag(s) to use for a given flow (what experiment/activity is ongoing) and a way to set them (for each packet in principle).

Approximations to the ideal case where all traffic is marked by experiment/activity should also be considered (it's reasonable to assume that tagging the core amount of traffic will be sufficient, but partial tagging should also be investigated, i.e. if we can only tag experiment but not activity in certain cases). We assume Linux-based applications (?) and therefore require interface(s) either to the Linux kernel (application directly setting tags and kernel issuing packets with that tag) or ways how Linux-based systems could interact with network equipment (e.g. possible valid use cases could be if

V1.0

OpenStack/Kubernetes tenant network is mapped to an experiment tag via translation table and tagging is performed by the network equipment then).

Further we assume that information needed to tag the packets can be communicated between experiments/stakeholders and resource providers in an automated way.

Tags should be transferable across R&E networks (i.e. tags once set by the application at the source should reach destination unchanged). Tag specifications and its operation across NRENs (or even across public Internet) will require some form of standardisation process, at the very least in the WLCG, but potentially in a wider standardisation body. The marking approach must not break any existing standards, e.g. those that define IPv6 in the IETF (RFC 8200, etc). TBA

RNTWG: Packet Marking	1
Packet Marking Technologies/Standards	4
IP version 6	4
IP version 6 Flow Labels	4
Linux kernel support of the IPv6 flow label	5
Using an IPv6 Hop-by-Hop or Destination Option	6
Using IPv6 addressing	7
IPv6 Linux Kernel Implementation Details	8
Marking in the Payload	11
IP version 4	11
Linux kernel support	12
MPLS	12
Linux kernel support	13
Packet Marking Standardisation	14
Packet Marking Validation	14
Networking (R&E) Perspective	15
Marking transparency	15
Traffic inspection and collection on path	15
IPFIX protocol	15
Hardware export support for IPFIX IPv6 flow label (field #31)	15
Software collector support for IPFIX IPv6 flow label (field #31)	16
sFlow	16
Hardware/software support for flow label	16
Raw capture	16
Applications Perspective	17
(WLCG) Experiments Perspective	17
Deliverables	18
Timelines	18
Metrics for Success	18

Packet Marking Technologies/Standards

This part describes potential standards/technologies that could be used for packet marking and explains them in detail.

IP version 6

IP version 6 Flow Labels

IP version 6 has a dedicated 20-bit flow label in the headers

		Fixed header format																															
Offsets	Octet	0								1								2								3							
Octet	Bit	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
0	0	Version				Traffic Class				Flow Label																							
4	32	Payload Length																Next Header								Hop Limit							
8	64	Source Address																															
12	96																																
16	128																																
20	160																																
24	192																																
28	224	Destination Address																															
32	256																																
36	288																																

RFC covering its use cases are:

<https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc6437> (previous one was <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc3697>)

From [RFC6437]:

“The 20-bit Flow Label field in the IPv6 header [RFC2460] is used by a node to label packets of a flow. A Flow Label of zero is used to indicate packets that have not been labeled. Packet classifiers can use the triplet of Flow Label, Source Address, and Destination Address fields to identify the flow to which a particular packet belongs. Packets are processed in a flow-specific manner by nodes that are able to do so in a stateless manner or that have been set up with flow-specific state.”

“Once set to a non-zero value, the Flow Label is expected to be delivered unchanged to the destination node(s). A forwarding node MUST either leave a non-zero flow label value unchanged or change it only for compelling operational security reasons as described in [Section 6.1](#).”

Further discussion in section 4 of [RFC6436] reflects that the updated specification of the flow label imparts the following operational properties which can be summarized as:

- Sending hosts that are not updated will in practice continue to send all-zero labels.
- Sending hosts conforming to the new specification will by default choose uniformly distributed labels between 1 and 0xFFFFF.
- The expected default usage of the flow label is some form of stateless load distribution, such as the ECMP/LAG usage defined in [RFC6438].
- If the new rules are followed, all IPv6 traffic flows on the Internet should have zero or uniformly distributed flow label values.

Consideration should be made as to our compliance in overloading this field with respect to the specifications, namely that uniformly distributed flow labels could be required to keep the desired amount of entropy available in the packet headers. Use of a statically defined tag allocation scheme that is not uniformly distributed across the 20 bits would appear non-compliant. Mixing both marked flow tags as well as standard [\[RFC6437\]](#) randomly distributed labels may also complicate an analysis system needing to disambiguate the two. Note that [\[RFC6437\]](#) also allows routers to rewrite the flow label to a randomly distributed value if the label in the packet is set to zero.

Furthermore, [Section 6.1](#) of [\[RFC6437\]](#) suggests that

“In situations where the covert channel risk is considered significant, the only certain defense is for a firewall to rewrite non-zero flow labels. This would be an exceptional violation of the rule that the flow label, once set to a non-zero value, must not be changed. To preserve load distribution capability, such a firewall SHOULD rewrite labels by following the method described for a forwarding node (see [Section 3](#)), as if the incoming label value were zero, and MUST NOT set non-zero flow labels to zero.”

which could pose a challenge in getting the traffic marked at the source though the firewall boundaries of sites, if not with the current but with the future implementations of high performance real hardware based firewalls.

Linux kernel support of the IPv6 flow label

IPv6 flow label - Linux kernel interface:

IPv6 flow label is fully supported in the Linux kernel via standard socket interface, the following call can be made to tag packets:

```
setsockopt(s, IPPROTO_IPV6, IPV6_FLOWINFO_SEND, &opt, sizeof(opt))
```

E.g. [iperf3 implementation](#); <https://manpages.debian.org/stretch/manpages/ipv6.7.en.html>

Sample implementations are available in standard network tools such as ping and iperf3

The default in modern Linux distributions is for the kernel to automatically assign flow labels in accordance with [\[RFC6438\]](#). This behavior can be managed via sysctl:

```
/proc/sys/net/ipv6/auto_flowlabels - INTEGER
  Automatically generate flow labels based on a flow hash of the
  packet. This allows intermediate devices, such as routers, to
  identify packet flows for mechanisms like Equal Cost Multipath
  Routing (see RFC 6438).
  0: automatic flow labels are completely disabled
  1: automatic flow labels are enabled by default, they can be
    disabled on a per socket basis using the IPV6_AUTOFLOWLABEL
    socket option
  2: automatic flow labels are allowed, they may be enabled on a
    per socket basis using the IPV6_AUTOFLOWLABEL socket option
  3: automatic flow labels are enabled and enforced, they cannot
    be disabled by the socket option
  Default: 1
```

For any host running the flow label accounting scheme, it is likely this would need to be set to 0 on the host in order to disambiguate meaningful accounting data for traffic that has assigned flow tags vs traffic that would be assigned a random value by the kernel.

It is noteworthy that the `/proc/sys/net/ipv6/*flowlabel*` options are available in the RHEL based Linux distributions only starting from version 8.0 (currently provided with kernel v4.18.0-80.el8 - as of May 2020) while RHEL 7.x based distributions (currently RHEL 7.7 provided with kernel v3.10.0-1062.12.1.el7 - as of May 2020) don't have them exposed. Since WLCG collaborations (e.g. ATLAS) are specifying the range of Linux distributions that can be deployed on their CPU resources on sites rather strictly, and the transitions from one major OS version to another usually takes prolonged periods, this factor should be taken into account while putting forward the schedule for the packed marking to be deployed on sites.

This link shows an example of setting the flow label via setsockopt options:

https://github.com/esnet/ipperf/blob/666040bd791ad838ab671e523f9347d0f4c3dbec/src/ipperf_tcp.c#L548

```
#if
defined(HAVE
_FLOWLABEL)

    if (test->settings->flowlabel) {
        if (server_res->ai_addr->sa_family != AF_INET6) {
            saved_errno = errno;
            close(s);
            freeaddrinfo(server_res);
            errno = saved_errno;
            i_errno = IESETFLOW;
            return -1;
        } else {
            struct sockaddr_in6* sa6P = (struct sockaddr_in6*)
server_res->ai_addr;
            char freq_buf[sizeof(struct in6_flowlabel_req)];
            struct in6_flowlabel_req *freq = (struct in6_flowlabel_req
*)freq_buf;
            int freq_len = sizeof(*freq);

            memset(freq, 0, sizeof(*freq));
            freq->flr_label = htonl(test->settings->flowlabel &
IPV6_FLOWINFO_FLOWLABEL);
            freq->flr_action = IPV6_FL_A_GET;
            freq->flr_flags = IPV6_FL_F_CREATE;
            freq->flr_share = IPV6_FL_S_ANY;
            memcpy(&freq->flr_dst, &sa6P->sin6_addr, 16);

            if (setsockopt(s, IPPROTO_IPV6, IPV6_FLOWLABEL_MGR, freq,
freq_len) < 0) {
                saved_errno = errno;
                close(s);
                freeaddrinfo(server_res);
            }
        }
    }
#endif
```

```

        errno = saved_errno;
        i_errno = IESETFLOW;
        return -1;
    }
    sa6P->sin6_flowinfo = freq->flr_label;

    opt = 1;
    if (setsockopt(s, IPPROTO_IPV6, IPV6_FLOWINFO_SEND, &opt,
sizeof(opt)) < 0) {
        saved_errno = errno;
        close(s);
        freeaddrinfo(server_res);
        errno = saved_errno;
        i_errno = IESETFLOW;
        return -1;
    }
}
}
}

```

Note, if we want to use the “entropy” bits to instead create a Hamming code to identify “real” labels vs the entropy use-case, we will need to re-arrange the bit order to provide the calculation. See proposed bit definition scheme below for a more detailed discussion. More information at <https://medium.com/swlh/hamming-code-generation-correction-with-explanations-using-c-codes-38e700493280>

Using an IPv6 Hop-by-Hop or Destination Option

In support of [\[RFC8321\]](#) for SRv6, the IETF draft <https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-ietf-6man-ipv6-alt-mark-00> faces some of the same challenges in trying to overload the IPv6 flow label for its use (a telemetry use-case outlined in [draft-ietf-ippm-multipoint-alt-mark](#) performance monitoring):

"Several alternatives have been analysed in [\[I-D.fioccola-v6ops-ipv6-alt-mark\]](#) such as IPv6 Extension Headers, IPv6 Address and Flow Label. The preferred choice would be the use of a new TLV to be encoded in the Option (Hop-by-Hop or Destination) Header."

The authors of the alt-mark draft have been contacted to explore synergies in the work. The draft has recently (May 2020) been formally adopted as a 6man WG draft.

One example of an (Experimental) published RFC using the Destination Option in such a way is RFC 7837 which defines a marking in support of congestion control (ConEx):

"The ConEx information can be used by any network element on the path to, for example, do traffic management or egress policing."

Another example is RFC 8250, which is a Standards Track document that defines a destination option for Performance and Diagnostic Metrics (PDM) for IPv6.

There is also this draft defining an option - <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-ippm-ioam-ipv6-options/>, the use case being carrying OAM information.

The Destination option header could therefore be a logical choice to place application-specific telemetry identifiers, as there is less of a constraint on space than the IPv6 Flow Label, less history of defined pre-existing intentions from the standards body, and low deployed usage on the Internet. However, at present, the linux implementation in particular requires either `setuid 0` or `CAP_NET_RAW` capability to be able to call `setsockopt(s, IPPROTO_IPV6, IPV6_DSTOPTS, ext_hdr_p, ext_hdr_size)`. There has been a set of patches made that could address this as well as extend the functionality, though they have [not been met with support from the linux network maintainers](#). Additionally, extracting that field from intermediate routers and exporting it via IPFIX may not be practical.

While in principle it's possible, it is less practical to use a Hop-by-Hop option, for the reasons discussed in [draft-krishnan-ipv6-hopbyhop-05](#). There is however a recent draft that proposes its use - [draft-ietf-6man-mtu-option-02](#). If you want to signal to routers on the path that they should process the option, then a HBH option is appropriate, BUT routers will not process it unless configured to do so, and if not, they may well drop the packet. The question is what types of devices do we want to process the Option? If it's (say) P4 devices, then they should be able to inspect a Destination Option.

There is an IANA registry of Destination and HBH Options at <https://www.iana.org/assignments/ipv6-parameters/ipv6-parameters.xhtml> [IPDM has a registered option, while ConEx uses an experimental value \(0x1E\)](#).

RFC 7872 discusses the dropping of packets using IPv6 EHs. This implies testing of the approach would be important, as discussed further below in this document. Drops may be less of a problem between consenting sites that know how to configure their firewalls, such as the LHCONE / LHCOPN in WLCG, but perhaps less so at specific other campuses.

Using IPv6 addressing

Given the size of IPv6 addresses, it is possible to mark or "colour" packets by using specific site network prefixes (within a site /64) or values in (a part of) the host part of the address (64 bits). Hosts already currently use multiple IPv6 source addresses. Applications would need to map to the correct source address.

Challenges:

- Adding an IP address requires root (knewell - I'm not familiar with the system support ecosystem for WLCG - is it a challenge to coordinate adding an address. Additionally, how dynamic is one endpoint in regards to different marked flows - i.e., will an endpoint require hundreds of addresses or only a handful?)
- Applications will need to be able to bind to a source address. This may not be feasible if one application supports multiple flows that need different markings
- Need to disambiguate from random sources addresses
 - Suggestion 1
 - use the 64 bits of the host portion

- set the first 16 bits to a known value, e.g., AAAA (cursory investigation of IPv6 source addresses on Internet2 (24 hour time frame) indicates no host portions starting with that value; should investigate RFCs - determine if there's a value we would never expect to show up but could use)
- Remaining 48 bits used for marking label
- Additionally, we could use a byte or nibble as a checksum, further reducing the likelihood of a random address colliding with our label space
- {network 64 bits}:AAAA:xxxx:xxxx:yyhh
 - AAAA = signals this is a marked packet (16 bits)
 - xxxx:xxxx = used for label space (32 bits)
 - yy = checksum calculated on previous 32 (8 bits)
 - hh = host; supports multiple hosts on the same subnet (8 bits)
- Does this decrease entropy for hashing? Initial thoughts indicate no - a server would typically use one address and the source or dest port is random - that's still the case. Security concerns
 - Multiple and/or changing source addresses create a moving target for ACL management

Items to investigate:

- Can we create a shim application (akin to a proxy or load balancer or NAT) that translates the IP address of a flow (e.g., based on some signal from the application, the source IP is translated appropriately)? netfilter?

IPv6 Linux Kernel Extension Headers Details

The existing IPv6 extension headers are currently surveyed at

<https://www.iana.org/assignments/ipv6-parameters/ipv6-parameters.xhtml>

Protocol Number	Description	Reference
0	IPv6 Hop-by-Hop Option	[RFC8200]
43	Routing Header for IPv6	[RFC8200][RFC5095]
44	Fragment Header for IPv6	[RFC8200]
50	Encapsulating Security Payload	[RFC4303]
51	Authentication Header	[RFC4302]
60	Destination Options for IPv6	[RFC8200]
135	Mobility Header	[RFC6275]
139	Host Identity Protocol	[RFC7401]
140	Shim6 Protocol	[RFC5533]
253	Use for experimentation and testing	[RFC3692][RFC4727]
254	Use for experimentation and testing	[RFC3692][RFC4727]

Latest Linux kernel implementation has the following [definitions](#) of the implemented option headers:

```

#define NEXTHDR_HOP          0      /* Hop-by-hop option header. */
#define NEXTHDR_TCP          6      /* TCP segment. */
#define NEXTHDR_UDP          17     /* UDP message. */
#define NEXTHDR_IPV6        41     /* IPv6 in IPv6 */
#define NEXTHDR_ROUTING     43     /* Routing header. */
#define NEXTHDR_FRAGMENT    44     /* Fragmentation/reassembly header. */
#define NEXTHDR_GRE         47     /* GRE header. */
#define NEXTHDR_ESP         50     /* Encapsulating security payload. */
#define NEXTHDR_AUTH        51     /* Authentication header. */
#define NEXTHDR_ICMP        58     /* ICMP for IPv6. */
#define NEXTHDR_NONE        59     /* No next header */
#define NEXTHDR_DEST        60     /* Destination options header. */
#define NEXTHDR_SCTP        132    /* SCTP message. */
#define NEXTHDR_MOBILITY    135    /* Mobility header. */

#define NEXTHDR_MAX         255

```

This maps to the IANA assignments as follows:

- Hop-by-Hop and Destination Options (0 and 60) [RFC8200](#)
- Routing headers (43, [RFC8200](#))
 - This function is very similar to IPv4's Loose Source and Record Route option.
- Authentication header and security payload (50, 51, [RFC4303](#), [RFC4302](#))
 - IP Authentication Header (AH) is used to provide connectionless integrity and data origin authentication for IP datagrams and to provide protection against replays.
 - Encapsulating Security Payload (ESP) protocol, which is designed to provide a mix of security services in IPv4 and IPv6. ESP is used to provide confidentiality, data origin authentication, connectionless integrity, an anti-replay service (a form of partial sequence integrity), and limited traffic flow confidentiality.
- Mobility header (135, [RFC6275](#))
 - Mobile IPv6 is a protocol that allows nodes to remain reachable while moving around in the IPv6 Internet. Each mobile node is always identified by its home address, regardless of its current point of attachment to the Internet.
- Stream Control Transmission Protocol - SCTP (132, [RFC4960](#))
- Generic Routing Encapsulation - GRE (47, [RFC7676](#))
- Others: TCP, UDP, ICMP, Fragmentation, etc.

Implementation [history](#) shows most of this was implemented by 2017, since then there are only few additions.

Hop-by-Hop and Destination Options has the following limits (added Nov/2017; can be set via sysctl):

- **max_dst_opts_number** - INTEGER
 - Maximum number of non-padding TLVs allowed in a Destination options extension header. If this value is less than zero then unknown options are disallowed and the number of known TLVs allowed is the absolute value of this number.

Default: 8

- **max_hbh_opts_number** - INTEGER
Maximum number of non-padding TLVs allowed in a Hop-by-Hop options extension header. If this value is less than zero then unknown options are disallowed and the number of known TLVs allowed is the absolute value of this number.
Default: 8
- **max_dst_opts_length** - INTEGER
Maximum length allowed for a Destination options extension header.
Default: INT_MAX (unlimited)
- **max_hbh_length** - INTEGER
 - Maximum length allowed for a Hop-by-Hop options extension header.
 - Default: INT_MAX (unlimited)

IPv6 flow labels appear to have stable implementation with only few [changes](#) submitted in 2018/2019 (none in 2020) and follow RFCs [6437](#), [6438](#), [7690](#).

Sysctl parameters currently implemented are as follows:

- **auto_flowlabels** - INTEGER
Automatically generate flow labels based on a flow hash of the packet. This allows intermediate devices, such as routers, to identify packet flows for mechanisms like Equal Cost Multipath Routing (see RFC 6438).
0: automatic flow labels are completely disabled
1: automatic flow labels are enabled by default, they can be disabled on a per socket basis using the IPV6_AUTOFLOWLABEL socket option
2: automatic flow labels are allowed, they may be enabled on a per socket basis using the IPV6_AUTOFLOWLABEL socket option
3: automatic flow labels are enabled and enforced, they cannot be disabled by the socket option
- **flowlabel_state_ranges** - BOOLEAN
Split the flow label number space into two ranges. 0-0x7FFFF is reserved for the IPv6 flow manager facility, 0x80000-0xFFFFF is reserved for stateless flow labels as described in RFC6437.
- **flowlabel_reflect** - INTEGER
Control flow label reflection. Needed for Path MTU Discovery to work with Equal Cost Multipath Routing in anycast environments. See RFC 7690 and: <https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-wang-6man-flow-label-reflection-01>
This is a bitmask.
1: enabled for established flows
Note that this prevents automatic flowlabel changes, as done in "tcp: change IPv6 flow-label upon receiving spurious retransmission" and "tcp: Change txhash on every SYN and RTO retransmit"
2: enabled for TCP RESET packets (no active listener)
If set, a RST packet sent in response to a SYN packet on a closed port will reflect the incoming flow label.
4: enabled for ICMPv6 echo reply messages.
- **seg6_flowlabel** - INTEGER

Controls the behaviour of computing the flowlabel of outer IPv6 header in case of SR T.encaps

- **flowlabel_consistency** - BOOLEAN

Protect the consistency (and unicity) of flow label.

You have to disable it to use IPV6_FL_F_REFLECT flag on the flow label manager.

Marking in the Payload

Marking in the payload is out of scope given the increased prevalence of TLS/SSL/etc, which means that payloads cannot be inspected on path.

Network Tokens

A recently published IETF personal draft documents the concept of “Network Tokens”, see <https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-yiakoumis-network-tokens-01>.

“A network token is a small piece of data that end users attach to their packets. As packets flow through the network, intermediate nodes MAY detect tokens, interpret them, and apply the desired service to the packets that carry them (and possibly to all other packets from the same flow).

For example, a token might just state the name of the application that a packet originates from”

The draft proposes a 28-bit token ID field. It discusses multiple mechanisms for tokens to be conveyed; some may be applicable to IPv4.

IP version 4

IPv4 doesn't have a dedicated flow label, but provides a way to extend headers by means of header options. An overview of the IPv4 RFCs related to the header options can be found at:

<https://www.iana.org/assignments/ip-parameters/ip-parameters.xhtml>

IPv4 Header Format																																	
Offsets	Octet	0						1						2						3													
Octet	Bit	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
0	0	Version			IHL			DSCP			ECN			Total Length																			
4	32	Identification						Flags			Fragment Offset																						
8	64	Time To Live			Protocol			Header Checksum																									
12	96	Source IP Address																															
16	128	Destination IP Address																															
20	160	Options (if IHL > 5)																															
24	192																																
28	224																																
32	256																																

There is an IETF draft that attempts to add IPv6 flow labels to IPv4 via options at <https://tools.ietf.org/html/draft-herbert-ipv4-eh-01>, however there appears to be no existing implementation of it.

Linux kernel support

IPv4 header options can be set via setsockopt as well, however the actual application support for different standards is more complex. While there are many existing IPv4 header options (<https://www.iana.org/assignments/ip-parameters/ip-parameters.xhtml>), only some of them are implemented in the Linux kernel. From the existing IP options, the following are mentioned in the [kernel headers](#):

- RR - record route
- L/SRRR - strict and loose source routing and record route
- RA - router alert
- TS - timestamps
- SID - stream ID
- SEC - security ID
- CIPSO - commercial security ID

Attempts to patch iperf3 to add IPv4 header options to its streams worked for RR and TS. However for SID and SEC, which are actually closest to any “tagging” functionality we could use, none of the attempts were successful. It appears that the implementation for those in the kernel is [empty](#).

Further, <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc1122#page-35> obsoletes SID (which would be perfect, it's exactly 16 bits tag) and states that only options that are well understood should be implemented.

The final one is CIPSO, which actually has an implementation in the kernel (done by HP) and is kind of “selinux” for networks, so one can run an audit on packets and discard anything that is not labeled correctly. However, labeling does require additional configuration of the node to indicate which label/DOI the node is part of and that seems rather complex to setup and appears to be designed to support **system-level tagging not application-level** (wasn't tested as it didn't work out of the box on CentOS7).

MPLS

Multiprotocol Label Switching (MPLS) is a routing technique in telecommunications networks that directs data from one node to the next based on short path labels rather than long network addresses, thus avoiding complex lookups in a routing table and speeding traffic flows. The labels identify virtual

links (paths) between distant nodes rather than endpoints. MPLS can encapsulate packets of various network protocols, hence the "multiprotocol" reference on its name. MPLS supports a range of access technologies

MPLS dates back to 1994 and one of its core use cases is the operation of the L3 VPNs.

MPLS works by prefixing packets with an MPLS header, containing one or more labels. This is called a label *stack*. Each entry in the label stack contains four fields:

- A 20-bit label value. A label with the value of 1 represents the *router alert label*.
- a 3-bit *Traffic Class* field for QoS (*quality of service*) priority and ECN (*Explicit Congestion Notification*). Prior to 2009 this field was called EXP.^[8]
- a 1-bit *bottom of stack* flag. If this is set, it signifies that the current label is the last in the stack.
- an 8-bit TTL (*time to live*) field.

MPLS Label																															
00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Label																				TC: Traffic Class (QoS and ECN)			S: Bottom-of-Stack			TTL: Time-to-Live					

Recently, MPLS has been proposed to be used in the design of the cloud native data centre networks (<https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc8670>).

Linux kernel support

TBA

One possible way to insert MPLS labels is to use openvswitch, which has standard interface to Linux kernel via kernel module (to be determined how applications could interact with OVS). Another would be [VPP](#), which is another established datapath/switch.

Packet Marking Standardisation

A means will be required to set the marking values, and have a common understanding of the semantics of those values.

The number of bits required for the marking needs to be agreed.

While 20 bits may suffice for WLCG, it may hamper wider adoption by other global R&E endeavours.

Some form of registry will be required.

To start we could agree on a URL to publish the markings we define. However we will need to somehow standardize the bit definitions and define the process for updating it as new science domains or traffic types are introduced. We have been discussing a marking scheme which is similar to the network/host differentiation we use in sub-netting with network replaced by science domain (owner) and host replaced by traffic type. Some have suggested differentiating traffic purpose and application to have different sets of bits. We could leave the traffic type up to each owner (each could have their own definition of the bits that they would need to publish) or we try to enforce some kind of standard, or we make a mix of the two.

To this end we have a draft specification of the usage of the 20 bits from the flow label use-case at <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1KOkZxmCtLoU2y5DKGjvQEo-A-A3kUN2UgnWlqF-4zoQ/edit?usp=sharing>

Science Domain	Application	H dr																			
		Bit 12	Bit 13	Bit 14	Bit 15	Bit 16	Bit 17	Bit 18	Bit 19	Bit 20	Bit 21	Bit 22	Bit 23	Bit 24	Bit 25	Bit 26	Bit 27	Bit 28	Bit 29	Bit 30	Bit 31
		Bit 19	Bit 18	Bit 17	Bit 16	Bit 15	Bit 14	Bit 13	Bit 12	Bit 11	Bit 10	Bit 9	Bit 8	Bit 7	Bit 6	Bit 5	Bit 4	Bit 3	Bit 2	Bit 1	Bit 0
Reserved	Reserved	x	x	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	x	0	0	0	0	0	0	x	x
ATLAS	<ANY>	x	x	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
<ANY>	performance	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	0	0	0	0	0	1	x	x

CM	perfSONAR																				
		x	x	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	x	0	0	0	0	0	1	x	x
S	R	x	x									x								x	x

The fourth tab has the current complete bit listing.

One concern was a random collision between our proposed packet marking format above and the default use-case of providing pseudo-random entropy in the flow-label field. If this is a concern we could repurpose the “entropy” bits highlighted in light red in the above diagram) to instead create a Hamming code. To do this we would need to logically re-arrange the bits for the Hamming calculation.

Packet Marking Validation

Whichever approach is preferred, testing and validation of the packet marking will be required.

The marking must

1. Arrive at the destination node unaltered from its initially set value
2. Be readable by any node on the path where consumption and action on the marking may be required
3. Not cause unintended interoperability issues with other protocols

Thus one validation would need to check the end to end transparency of the marking, while another would need to demonstrate an on-path device acting on the marking.

Relevant earlier work in RFC 7872 has shown that IPv6 packets with EHS may get dropped along the path. The tests used to determine this in this RFC were largely based on sending traffic towards public web servers. In our case, a client-server approach may be more appropriate. Fernando Gont (an author of RFC 7872) has written a variety of tools that may be useful, or readily ported to be so, as part of his IPv6 Toolkit (see <https://www.sifnetworks.com/tools/ipv6toolkit/>). We have approached Fernando to enquire.

A longer term goal may be to add a new test type to perfSONAR and leverage the existing perfSONAR WLCG infrastructure to validate the markings pass unaltered on an ongoing basis.

Networking (R&E) Perspective

This section reflects on the NREN perspective related to the previously described technologies. Some relevant questions to answer would be:

- What/how stats can be retrieved
- What network equipment/devices/standards are needed
- What's the potential deployment complexity (across R&E landscape)
- Potential for future network orchestration related to given approach
- ...

Marking transparency

NREN operators should not apply mechanisms that alter the marking of packets as those packets transit their networks.

Traffic inspection and collection on path

IPFIX protocol

If packets were marked using the IPv6 flow label, it may be possible for intermediate routers to sample traffic in the forwarding hardware and send this data off to central collectors for analysis. In many network environments, the standard approach is for a hardware-specific implementation on a router to sample the traffic and use the IPFIX (or Netflow v9) protocol to send the sampled data to a collector. The IPFIX standard supports field #31 for the IPv6 Flow Label, though router hardware and collector software may or may not support this.

Hardware export support for IPFIX IPv6 flow label (field #31)

- Nokia 7750
 - supported for non-encapsulated packets
 - not supported on MPLS-encapsulated packets.
 - Note, all LHCOPN and LHCONE traffic on ESnet is MPLS-encapsulated.
 - ESnet is asking Nokia about the viability of hardware and firmware support for encapsulated packets.
- Juniper
 - [Not supported](#)
- Cisco
 - **Supported on at least IOS-XR 7.0.12**
- Arista
 - does not support IPFIX

Software collector support for IPFIX IPv6 flow label (field #31)

- nfcapd / nfdump
 - supports collection of field 31 and writes it to disk
 - reading field #31 w/ nfdump is not supported

- ESnet has a patch for nfdump, and is working to submit it upstream
- tshark
 - supported
- splunk
 - supported

sFlow

Some hardware platforms, primarily with a lineage more firmly rooted in switching support traffic sampling via sflow. Unlike ipfix/netflow, the traffic is not summarized by the router/switch, but a significant part of the sampled raw packet is encapsulated and sent to the collector for analysis. sFlow datagrams include one or more packet flow records which in turn include the original datagram header. Ability to extract individual fields such as the IPv6 flow label may vary depending on software used.

Hardware support for sFlow IPv6 flow labels

- *Likely unsupported on typical routing hardware platforms*
- *Possibly supported on some datacenter switches*
- Known platforms retaining correct flow label in samples
 - Dell EMC Networking OS9 (S6000-ON verified)
 - Dell EMC Networking OS10 (S4248FB-ON verified)

Software support for sFlow IPv6 flow labels

- Elastiflow
 - Utilizes Logstash Codec SFlow Plugin underneath
- sfcapd / nfdump
 - sfcapd stores sFlow captures into nfcapd files (ESnet patch above might work?)
 - (garhan will try to verify this can work)

Raw capture

Traffic mirroring and/or optical taps could be used to copy raw traffic to a server for analysis. The data rates, number of links, and power availability to run servers for collection may make traditional packet capture and analysis impractical in many nren environments.

With the advent of more sophisticated hardware such as programmable "smart" NICs with ASIC, NPU, or FPGAs, it could be possible to write a P4 program or similar acceleration to collect and aggregate data at high speeds.

There is work on P4 and data plane programmability in the GÉANT GN4-3 project, e.g. the RARE router project - <https://wiki.geant.org/display/RARE>. The teams there have asserted that inspecting the IPv6 packet header with P4 should not be a problem, but we would need to identify the actions we want to take on observing the values, and the line rates that need to be supported.

Traffic analysis

Corresponding to the expectations in section 4 of [\[RFC6436\]](#), a brief, unscientific sampling of non-MPLS encapsulated traffic collected via IPFIX on ESnet5 does show that there is a mix of [\[RFC3697\]](#) compliant hosts where all-zero flow labels are used, as well as updated [\[RFC6437\]](#) compliant hosts that by default choose uniformly distributed labels between 1 and 0xFFFFF.

A traffic analysis system may need to know whether a specific host is using the overloaded meaning of the flow label and that the field is relevant, vs trying to keep the accounting state for 2^{20} labels in use for each link of the network.

Applications Perspective

This section reflects on the applications perspective (storage providers, data management systems) related to the previously described technologies. Some relevant questions to answer would be:

- What are the potential ways applications can mark the packets, is there Linux kernel support, are there standard Linux API calls that can be used ?
- What libraries would need to be changed/tuned to get the marking across from application level to the kernel/packet API
- What information would be needed at the application level to mark the packets; what's missing (cf. experiments perspective)
- ...
- On what interval would this be set? Is there some central oracle bestowing tags? Is this a dynamic query? Or is this hard coded into something statically at job run time? Are the tags truly assigned per-flow at the application level?
- Once the application has its socket, it knows the full src,dst,ports tuple that can identify the flow. Could this be timestamped and sent to a central collector rather than tagging the packets?

(WLCG) Experiments Perspective

This section reflects on the experiments perspective (experiments data management operations, data access, etc.) related to the previously described technologies. Some relevant questions to answer would be:

- What activities, types of activities would be good candidates for marking
 - For ATLAS, we have a dedicated set of activities that we use (~20 different) which is mostly static. We need to identify at least these activities. There might be one or two occasions where the computeflow is interesting within a given activity, so it might add a handful for "sub-activity" flows, but in terms of packet marking this would just be on the same level as the others.
- How can/will activities propagate to the applications
 - The data management system would pass the activity information to the transfer service which passes the information to the source/destination storage.
- What would be required to tweak experiments worker node payload to support packet tagging (which libraries/software is used to transfer data to/from WN)
 - The source/destination storage (depending which endpoint takes the active part in the transfer), should be able to use the transfer metadata passed down from the data management system when doing the necessary network interaction (e.g., when opening sockets, etc.). This requires that participating storage systems understand the metadata, and can appropriately pass that information to the (OS-level?) network stack.

V1.0

- What changes would be needed in the experiments data management systems to support marking
 - Nothing major, as we are passing several types of metadata already to the storage system. The change would have to be done in the storage system software.
-

Deliverables

Timelines

Metrics for Success

Suggestions:

- Traffic belonging to a specific experiment can be marked at source
- There is an agreed mechanism to share / look up marking values for a given experiment
- The marked traffic passes end to end without the marking being altered; the marking is received as sent
- The marking can be read by at least one and preferably multiple tools / mechanisms on path.
- The marking method does not break any known standards (perhaps just IETF standards?)

Not sure what to say about publication of observed marked traffic into a visualisation tool (such as Netsage has now, for example).

Perhaps the timeline is to demonstrate the above for one experiment by Q1 2021?